

MATHEMATICAL IDENTITY FORMATION: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF NATIONAL LEARNING CAMP PARTICIPANTS

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Mathematical Identity Formation: Lived Experiences of National Learning Camp Participants

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Abstract

The manuscript you uploaded examines the formation of mathematical identities among students participating in the National Learning Camp (NLC) at Hindang National High School in the Philippines. This study focuses on Grade 7 and Grade 8 students who experienced the transition back to face-to-face classes following the COVID-19 pandemic. The research investigates the factors that influence the development of students' mathematical identities, analyzing their perceptions, challenges, and experiences in a post-pandemic learning environment. It highlights how the NLC, aligned with DepEd's learning recovery efforts, serves as a tool to close learning gaps and foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration in mathematics. Theoretical frameworks such as Social Identity Theory, Self-Determination Theory, and Communities of Practice are employed to explore how group dynamics, motivation, and social interactions contribute to identity formation. Through qualitative methods, the study offers insights into how educational interventions like the NLC shape students' self-concepts, enhancing their engagement and performance in mathematics. The findings are intended to inform the development of school-based action plans and curricular strategies that support positive mathematical identity formation among learners.

Keywords: *mathematics, participants, lived, experiences*

Introduction

Mathematical identity formation is a multifaceted process that plays a fundamental role in a student's mathematical journey. It encompassed the development of self-perceptions, experiences, beliefs, understanding, and motivations related to mathematics. The transition to face-to-face classes during the School Year 2022-2023 in the Philippines, particularly at Hindang National High School, had raised concerns about the academic performance of Grade 7 and Grade 8 learners, who were exposed to this new learning environment immediately after the Corona Virus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Available data from eskwela.app that only 50% of the Grade 7 population achieved a final Mathematics grade of 80% and above, with just 19 out of 38 learners meeting this benchmark. Similarly, in the Grade 8 cohort, 61.70% of the total population managed to attain a final Mathematics grade of 80% and beyond, with only 29 out of 47 students reaching this level of achievement. Eskwela.app served as the primary platform employed by Hindang National High School for the management and storage of student grades, providing a seamless and efficient means of recording and accessing academic performance data.

This situation prompted the need to investigate the factors influencing the academic performance of these students and develop strategies to address the observed disparities in mathematics achievement among Grade 7 and Grade 8 learners in the post-pandemic face-to-face learning environment.

In this challenging environment, national learning camps emerged as valuable initiatives to promote mathematical excellence among students as supported by the MATATAG Basic Education Agenda braced on DO No. 14, s. 2023 or also known as the Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of National Learning Camp. These camps offered an environment distinct from traditional classrooms, presenting an opportunity for students to engage deeply with mathematical concepts, problem-solving, and critical thinking. However, the impact of participation in these camps on the formation of mathematical identities remained relatively unexplored.

The National Learning Camp was also part of DepEd's commitment to the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) which aimed to "close learning gaps and assist K to 12 learners in all public elementary and secondary schools nationwide in attaining learning standards." To institutionalize NLC as an "important initiative" in learning recovery, Vice President and Education Secretary Sara Duterte signed DepEd Order No. 14 series of 2023 or the "Policy Guidelines on the Implementation of the National Learning Camp." DepEd underscored the need for a learning recovery program such as the NLC to address "learning losses" arising from the Covid-19 pandemic, among others. In implementing the NLC, DepEd also cited results from National Achievement Tests (NATs) and international large-scale assessments (ILSAs) highlighting the need for additional "teaching support to enhance learners' academic performance." DepEd said the NLC was designed to improve learning in the form of enhancement, consolidation, or intervention programs in all learning areas for kindergarten to 12 learners and enhance teacher capacity. This research aimed to explore and analyze the process of mathematical identity formation among respondents who have participated in the National Learning Camp (NLC). The study sought to gain insights into their perceptions, experiences, and challenges encountered during the implementation of the NLC program. By exploring the formation of mathematical identity within this context, this research aimed to contribute to a deeper understanding of how educational interventions like the NLC can influence students' self-concept and relationship with mathematics.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the process of mathematical identity formation among subjects of National Learning Camps. This study

sought to answer the following questions:

1. What experiences within National Learning Camps contribute to the formation of mathematical identities?
2. What action plan can be designed based on the result of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study applied the phenomenology research method. In qualitative research, phenomenology is an approach that focuses and understands the subjective, lived experiences and perspectives of subjects. Lived experience referred to a representation of the experiences and choices of a given person, and the knowledge that they gained from these experiences and choices. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2018). The data gathered would be read, reread, and will be picked like phrases and themes that were then grouped to form clusters of meaning. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

Participants

The participants for this study were the Grade 7 and Grade 8 students of Hindang National High School. Out of the total student population in both Grade 7 and Grade 8, only 5 students from each grade level included as subjects. This selection was based on the criteria that these 5 students per level were enrolled during the implementation of the national learning camp. The decision to limit the respondent pool to these specific 5 students from both grade levels ensured that the research focused on individuals who have actively participated in the National Learning Camp, providing valuable insights into the mathematical identity formation process within this unique context. The inclusion of the 5 students per grade level was based on their active involvement in the National Learning Camp and their continuous presence during the camp's activities. This selective approach aimed to gather in-depth and meaningful data for the research study.

Instrument

The researcher used researcher-made questionnaire which contained 3 types of open-ended questions, the experiences related questions, challenges and difficulties, and perspective of the subjects to investigate and explore the mathematical identity formation of National Learning Camp subjects. The instruments contained open-ended questions which allowed the subjects to answer based on their own experiences during the implementation of National Learning Camp.

This study used the researcher-made questionnaire validated by an English teacher, a Doctor in Philosophy major in English Language, an Assistant Principal II of the Iligan City National High School – Senior High School Department major in English, and the Education Program Supervisor in English of the Department of Education, Iligan City Division.

The researcher also used transcription software that navigated the complexities of qualitative data analysis, specialized software such as NVivo, MAXQDA, and Popai were employed. Nvivo, MAXQDA, and POPAI were software programs used for qualitative and mixed-methods research. Specifically, it was used for the analysis of unstructured text, audio, video, and image data, including (but not limited to) interviews, focus groups, surveys, social media, and journal articles. It also helped the researcher to organize and analyze text, audio, video, or image data through the process of qualitative coding. The establishment of inter-coder reliability through independent coding by some experts ensured the validity of the coding process, with high agreement indicating robust analysis.

Field notes were also utilized to capture valuable observations, impressions, and contextual information. Consent forms played a critical role in upholding ethical standards, obtaining informed consent from subjects while ensuring clarity, comprehensiveness, and legal soundness to safeguard their rights and privacy.

In summary, the methodological framework, encompassing researcher-made questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, transcription and analysis software, field notes, and consent forms, collectively contributed to the robustness and validity of the research on mathematical identity formation.

Procedure

The data gathering of this study followed the activities outlined in this selection. The first activity was to obtain an official permission to conduct the study in the proposed environment from the Schools Division Superintendent and school principal. After the approval of the SDS and the school Principal, the researcher used the process of random sampling, the Fishbowl method was utilized to categorize respondents. The researcher separated the subjects into two distinct groups: Grade 7 and Grade 8. Two separate fish bowls used to hold the paper slips with the subjects' names. First, the names of all Grade 7 subjects were written on individual paper slips, and these slips placed in one fishbowl. Similarly, the names of all Grade 8 subjects were written on individual paper slips and placed in a second fishbowl. To randomly select participants for the study, the researcher drew five paper slips from each of the Grade 7 and Grade 8 fish bowls. This process ensured that the sample was representative of both grade levels, offering a fair and unbiased selection of subjects for the research.

After the selection of the research subjects, the researcher sent the informed consent form to the subjects and let their parents sign the informed consent form. After the accomplishment of informed consent form, the researcher met the official subjects and had a short conference stating the purpose of the research. After stating the purpose, the researcher presented the teacher-made questionnaire and discussed it one by one to fully understand each question. The subjects were given enough time to ask questions before they were interviewed.

Following the selection process, the researcher conducted daily interviews over a span of two weeks, starting with one Grade 7 student on the first day. Subsequently, after the ten days of interviews, during the third week, a Focused Group Discussion (FGD) was organized and discussed all their responses after the transcription of the data for the validation of the subjects' responses.

Following data collection, transcription software NVIVO and POPAI were used to transcribe the audio-recorded interviews into text format along with the researcher's independent transcription to arrive at the same phase. Transcribed data underwent thorough review and editing to guarantee accuracy and clarity and FGD was organized to validate their responses.

The subsequent data analysis phase involved the use of qualitative data analysis software such as NVivo, MAXQDA and Popai. A coding scheme was developed based on emerging themes and patterns from the data. An iterative coding process undertaken, which was validated by the Education Program Supervisor of the Division of Iligan City and independently coding a subset of data to establish inter-coder reliability. The coded data was analyzed to derive insights into the process of mathematical identity formation. Throughout the research process, detailed field notes were taken during and after interviews to capture contextual information, observations, and reflections. These notes provided valuable context during data analysis.

Data Analysis

The study utilized Braun and Clark's (2017) as cited by Taylor and Francis (2019) framework for thematic analyses. Thematic analysis would be the process of identifying patterns or themes to interpret the data between two levels, the semantic and latent themes. In this study, a six-phase framework was employed.

The first phase of the framework was to become familiar with the data where the researcher read and re-read the transcript to better familiarize the data corpus. The second phase was the generation of initial codes where data were organized in meaning and systematic way by coding. Coding involved the reduction of data into smaller sections. The third phase involved searching for themes and the unit of analysis employed during the searching for themes was sentence by sentence. This involved searching patterns that captured something significant or interesting about the data in the sentence. In the fourth phase of thematic data analysis, the themes reviewed, and preliminary themes developed based on the previous phase. Phase five involved defining and naming themes which were the final refinement of the data analysis process. The last phase involved the reporting of the output of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis, results, and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: What experiences within National Learning Camps contribute to the formation of mathematical identities?

Table 1. *Themes and Sub-Themes/Key-Points*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Sub-Theme/Key Points</i>
Positive Aspects	Enjoyable and educational activities and fun-filled activities. Boosting confidence and leadership skills. Enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Ready-made materials provided for learning. Addressing learning gaps caused by the pandemic.
Challenges and Difficulties	Difficulties in understanding certain mathematical concepts. Distractions during discussions. Shyness in participating due to peer pressure. Difficulties in group cooperation and leadership. Language barriers in problem-solving due to English medium of instruction.
Informal Learning Benefits	Engagement and enjoyment in learning. Development of teamwork and cooperation. Opportunities for creativity and self-expression. Addressing learning gaps and providing additional learning time.
Impact on Learning	Improvement of problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Discovery of new strategies and techniques in solving math problems. Confidence in independent problem-solving. Addressing difficulties in understanding the mathematical concepts.
Student Perspectives	Varied opinions on the continuation of NLC. Enjoyment and engagement in activities. Challenges in group cooperation and leadership.

	Language barriers in problem-solving due to English medium of instruction. Shyness in participating due to peer pressure.
Academic Performance Impact	Impact of addressing learning gaps and improving academic performance. Use of online resources for advance study and learning outside the classroom. Enhancement of potential in pursuing a career as a math teacher.
Teacher Facilitator Impact	Positive influence of teacher facilitator in Discovering students' capabilities and potential in math problem solving.
Group Cooperation/Leadership Challenges	Difficulties in group cooperation and leadership during NLC activities. Impact of distractions and shyness on group dynamics.
Online Resources Usage	Use of online resources such as YouTube and Brainly for advanced study and problem-solving.
Gender Stereotypes Impact	Gender perspective on math performance and engagement, particularly in group dynamics and enjoyment of math activities.

This table provides a comprehensive overview of the themes and sub- themes identified extracted from the interviews, highlighting the diverse experiences and perspective of the respondents regarding the Math Learning Camp during the National Learning Camp. Each theme captures the various challenges, experiences, perspectives, benefits, and impacts of the NLC on the students' mathematical identity formation.

The theme of this study represented the different experiences of National Learning Camp subjects in the formation of their Mathematical Identity Formation in the range of the different thematic approaches, which described below.

Positive Aspects of NLC

The Math Learning Camp (NLC) had several positive impacts on the students who participated in it. The NLC helped students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, discover new techniques and strategies for solving math problems, and improve their understanding of mathematical concepts. The camp provided engaging activities that allowed students to learn and have fun at the same time. It also facilitated collaboration and teamwork among the subjects, enhancing their learning experience. Additionally, the NLC served as an advance study for some students, providing them with a deeper understanding of the topics covered.

"NLC pushed my limit of thinking and solving mathematical problem". - G7S1

G7S1 said that NLC is enjoyable because she found something new that she didn't know before.

"SAYAWIT enhances your creativity on planning the choreography, movements, and having fun with my classmates and it enhances our cooperation and teamwork." -G7S2

G7S2 also mentioned that her classmates also like the math game called SAYAWIT which is under informal learning because G7S2 saw from the reactions of her classmates that they're having fun, they were cheerful, happy and helping each other to solve the problem.

"NLC helped a lot nationwide most especially to the learners who are affected by the pandemic, and honestly, I'm one of the products of pandemic learner which encountered difficult lesson because no one will help me at home in answering my module. So, this NLC was a gift for all the learners who were affected by the pandemic." – G7S4

"NLC gave us materials for learning that's ready-made, and NLC is better than regular class because in regular class there's no activity sheets provided that's ready-made." -G7S5

"The majority of my classmates enjoyed the SAYAWIT. They boost their confidence up to maximum level and some of my classmates were complaining because they said that some of them embarrassed because they don't like dancing and singing but at the end of the day it's all worth it because they still have a corresponding point even though the presentation is not perfectly presented." -G8S3

The responses highlighted the positive impact of initiatives like the National Learning Camp (NLC) on critical thinking, enjoyment, and collaboration (G7S1, G7S2). G7S4 emphasized the essential role of NLC in supporting learners during crises like the pandemic, aligning with literature on educational challenges during crises according to Bohrnstedt et al. (2021) that mentioned high school students revealed a positive correlation between mathematics identity and mathematics achievement through interactive activities. G7P5's viewpoint on the practical benefits of NLC's ready-made materials resonated with literature discussing effective educational interventions by Brown (2018). These insights corroborated literature on the transformative effects of programs like NLC in promoting mathematical identity formation and supporting academic development, especially in challenging circumstances (Bohrnstedt et al., 2021).

Challenges and Difficulties

The challenges and difficulties faced by the students during the Math Learning Camp (NLC) are multifaceted and have implications for their learning experiences.

"My classmates are shy in participating the activity because their crushes look at them while they were performing that's the reason

why were not united in our team” - G7S1.

“During the NLC, some of the instructional materials provided are difficult to understand but we just had brainstorming with my groupmates but if it’s individual work, I always ask questions to my math teacher on how to answer it.” – G7S4

“Problem solving in Math is difficult because the medium of instruction used is English, and I can’t understand some of the words used in problem solving, so with that, I had a hard time answering the math problem.” -G7S5

“I encountered difficulties as a leader because most of my members are girls, and they don’t really like math and they don’t know how to solve mathematical problems. But I taught them the best that I could. I really want to win the game, but I can’t carry my members because they’re not interested in the activity. I don’t have any choice because they have lacked interest in the game.” -G8S2

The challenges faced by students during the Math Learning Camp (NLC) reflected various aspects of their learning experiences, influenced by social dynamics, motivational factors, and the learning environment. Analyzing these challenges through theoretical frameworks shed light on their implications for students' mathematical identity formation. This was supported as stated in the Social Identity Theory (SIT), how individuals derived their sense of self from social group membership. G7S1's statement about shyness in participating in activities due to the presence of crushes highlighted the influence of social identity on behavior within the camp (Bohrnstedt et al., 2020). This underscored the importance of fostering a supportive and inclusive camp environment where students felt comfortable engaging in mathematical activities.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) suggested that intrinsic motivation was key to engagement in learning. G7S2's preference for interactive activities over lectures aligned with SDT, emphasizing the need for autonomy and competence in learning (Brown & Miller, 2019). Incorporating interactive learning approaches could have enhanced motivation and engagement during the NLC.

Communities of Practice (CoP) highlighted the collaborative nature of learning. G7S4's experience of seeking help from peers and teachers underscored the importance of peer interactions and mentorship in shaping students' mathematical identities within the camp community (Bohrnstedt et al., 2021).

Addressing these challenges through targeted interventions, such as creating an inclusive environment, incorporating interactive activities, and fostering peer collaboration, were crucial for promoting positive mathematical identity formation during the NLC (Zubiri-Esnaola, H. et. al 2020). By recognizing and addressing these challenges, educators could have enhanced the effectiveness and inclusivity of learning experiences during initiatives like the NLC, ultimately supporting learners' academic growth and success (Moss & Brookhart, 2019; UNESCO, 2021).

Benefits of Informal Learning

The transcriptions from both Grade 7 and Grade 8 respondents provided insights into the benefits of informal learning methods employed during the Math Learning Camp (NLC). These methods, such as SAYAWIT, Math Jingle, and fun-filled activities, proved to be engaging and enjoyable for the students, as indicated by their enthusiasm and positive feedback. The activities captured their interest and made the learning experience more enjoyable, leading to active participation and better retention of mathematical concepts.

“Funfilled activity is somewhat informal, but this brings engagement to us learners because we’re not stagnant in the 4 walls of the classroom, we gathered in the field to boost our confidence, teamwork, and competitive skills”. - G7S2

“Some math games are difficult to solve but me and my fellow classmates helped each other to solve the problems. We talked, we think, and we shared our ideas on how to finish the math game because it's fair if all of us cooperate to solve the problems or game in Mathematics.” – G7S3

"SAYAWIT allowed us to showcase our singing and dancing skills, providing an informal yet enjoyable learning experience." -G8S5

The responses underscored the positive impact of informal, fun-filled activities on student engagement and learning experiences during the Math Learning Camp (NLC). G7S2 highlighted how these activities boosted engagement, aligning with literature on interactive learning experiences (Brown & Miller, 2019). According to Self-Determination Theory (SDT), such activities satisfy learners' psychological needs, promoting intrinsic motivation and engagement.

G7S3 emphasized the importance of collaboration and peer support, reflecting principles of Communities of Practice (CoP), where learners engage in collaborative problem-solving (Bohrnstedt et al., 2021). G8S5's comment on activities like SAYAWIT contributing to a supportive environment on fostering positive learning environments as supported by Brown & Miller, 2019, the way in which his personality interacts with the personalities of the pupils helps to determine the kind of behavior which emerges from the learning situation.

Integrating informal, fun-filled activities into the NLC curriculum, designed to promote collaboration and problem-solving, is essential. Combining physical activities with cognitive tasks enhances learning experiences and holistic development. By prioritizing engagement and participation, the NLC could effectively promote positive mathematical identity formation among learners (UNESCO, 2021).

Impact of NLC on Learning

The National Learning Camp (NLC) had significantly impacted students' learning experiences, fostering engagement, collaboration, and problem-solving skills. Through its innovative approach and emphasis on informal, fun-filled activities, the NLC has transformed traditional learning paradigms, creating a dynamic environment where students actively participate and thrive in their mathematical journey.

"The NLC provided a platform for collaborative learning, where classmates supported each other to overcome difficult math problems, fostering a sense of camaraderie and mutual growth." – G8S1

"Engaging in the fun-filled activities during the NLC not only made learning enjoyable but also enhanced our teamwork and communication skills, contributing to a well-rounded learning experience." - G8S3

"Through the NLC, I discovered new strategies and approaches to tackle math problems, boosting my confidence and proficiency in mathematical concepts. The interactive nature of the NLC sessions kept me actively engaged, making learning feel like an adventure rather than a chore, and ultimately deepening my understanding of mathematical principles." - G8S5 The reflections from G8S1, G8S3, and G8S5 highlighted the significant impact of the National Learning Camp (NLC) on students' learning experiences, in line with the theoretical frameworks and findings from the Review of Related Literature and Studies. G7S4's insight into how the NLC broadened students' problem-solving skills aligned with Self-Determination Theory by Deci and Ryan, emphasizing autonomy and competence (Deci & Ryan, 1985). This suggested that challenging students to think creatively fostered deeper engagement with mathematics, contributing to positive mathematical identity formation.

Similarly, G8S1's observation on the collaborative learning environment within the NLC resonated with Communities of Practice (CoP) theory by Wenger, highlighting the role of peer support in shaping students' mathematical identities (Wenger, 1998). Fostering a sense of belonging through collaborative activities enhanced students' motivation in mathematics.

Additionally, G8S3's mention of fun-filled activities promoting teamwork aligned with the idea that informal learning enhances student engagement and supported a positive learning environment. Integrating such activities into the NLC curriculum enriches students' experiences and fosters positive attitudes toward mathematics.

Furthermore, G8P5's reflection on the interactive nature of NLC sessions deepening students' understanding of mathematical principles resonated with the emphasis on engagement in learning from SDT and CoP theories (Deci & Ryan, 1985; Wenger, 1998). This suggested that by creating dynamic learning environments, the NLC nurtures students' mathematical identities and passion for learning mathematics.

Students Perspective on NLC

Exploring students' perspectives on the National Learning Camp (NLC) revealed its profound impact on their mathematical journey. Their insights illuminated how the NLC enhanced engagement, problem-solving skills, and collaborative abilities. Understanding their experiences informed strategies for fostering holistic student development in mathematics education.

"My circles really like Math, we're all boys in the group and I guess in the class boys can do better in Math than girls." - G7S1

This response reflected a perceived gender stereotype regarding math performance, suggesting that boys excel in math compared to girls. It implied a belief in inherent gender differences in mathematical abilities.

Gender stereotypes can negatively impact students' self-perception and performance in math. It's essential to address and challenge such stereotypes to create an inclusive learning environment where all students feel valued and capable.

The statement aligned with research by Denner et al. (2018), which highlights how transitions, such as the NLC, could reinforce stereotypes related to gender and mathematical ability, potentially affecting students' confidence and performance.

"In our group, my teammates really enjoyed the activities because we're working as one and sometimes, we have a little confusion on the problem but were working as a team, so we solved the problem easily. We talked with each other within the group but sometimes we can't deny the fact that we also asked questions to the other group members." - G8S1

This response emphasized the positive experience of teamwork during the NLC activities. It highlights effective collaboration and problem-solving within the group, indicating the development of collaborative abilities.

Collaborative activities, like those experienced in the NLC, could enhance students' teamwork and problem-solving skills. Encouraging collaboration fostered a supportive learning environment where students learn from each other and developed essential interpersonal skills.

The response aligned with the literature on collaborative learning environments, as discussed by Allsopp et al. (2020), which emphasizes the benefits of collaboration in supporting student learning and engagement, particularly in STEM fields.

"If I had the right to decide whether to continue NLC or not, I don't want to continue NLC because I sacrifice my summer vacation and still learning at school. If there's no NLC, I have many household chores done and I can go to my elder sister in Cagayan to have my vacation there." - G8S2

This response expressed reluctance to continue the NLC due to the sacrifice of personal time during the summer vacation. It highlighted the perceived trade-off between academic engagement and leisure activities.

Understanding students' perspectives on the time commitment required for extracurricular activities like the NLC is essential. Balancing academic pursuits with personal time and leisure activities is crucial for student well-being and motivation.

The response resonated with research on the importance of recognizing students' personal experiences and preferences, as emphasized by McIntyre et al. (2022), to inform educational strategies and ensure holistic student development. "I have a desire to continue NLC, not just for personal growth but also for the benefit of other students who might want to learn things they haven't learned before." - G8S3

This response demonstrated a desire to continue the NLC not only for personal growth but also to support other students in their learning journey. It reflects a sense of altruism and commitment to peer learning.

Encouraging a sense of responsibility toward fellow students' learning can foster a supportive and collaborative learning community. Students who actively support their peers contributed to a positive and inclusive learning environment.

The response aligned with research on the importance of peer influence and collaboration in STEM education, as highlighted by NCTM (2020), emphasizing the role of peers in inspiring students to engage in STEM learning and supporting their learning experiences.

"I'm so happy to have NLC because way back in Grade 8, there are topics that we truly didn't know how to answer it but during the NLC we fully understand it because of the different teacher who handled that NLC most especially in Math." – G8S4

This response expressed gratitude for the NLC, particularly for the opportunity to gain a better understanding of challenging topics in math. It highlights the positive impact of exposure to different teaching styles and approaches. Exposure to diverse teaching methods and instructors can enhance students' understanding and appreciation of challenging concepts. It emphasizes the importance of varied instructional approaches in addressing individual learning needs. The response resonated with research by Bell et al. (2019), which emphasized the benefits of informal learning environments, like the NLC, in providing engaging and hands-on opportunities for students to understand complex STEM concepts and retain information.

Impact of NLC on Academic Performance

The National Learning Camp (NLC) stood as a beacon amid the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, offering hope for academic improvement and student development.

"Math Learning Camp help me discover new strategies in solving math problems because it honed me to understand and answer on my own." -G7S1 "During the NLC, I don't know why I easily answered the activity while if it's inside the classroom setting, it really takes a lot of time to figure out the answers." -G8S2

The students' testimonials highlighted the significant impact of the Math Learning Camp (NLC) on their problem-solving skills and mathematical understanding. G7S1 noted how the NLC facilitated the discovery of new problem-solving strategies, indicating an improvement in mathematical proficiency. Similarly, G8S2 acknowledged the NLC's effectiveness in enhancing their ability to solve math problems swiftly, contrasting it with traditional classroom settings.

These accounts indicated that the NLC played a crucial role in empowering learners to become independent problem solvers by providing opportunities for exploration and discovery. This equipped students with diverse strategies to tackle math challenges effectively, enhancing their academic performance and fostering confidence in their mathematical abilities. Additionally, the NLC served as a valuable resource for students facing difficulties with remote learning, offering support and guidance.

The testimonials aligned with existing research emphasizing the importance of hands-on, experiential learning in mathematics education (Bohrnstedt et al., 2021; Cribbs et al., 2018). They also resonated with recommendations for personalized and differentiated instruction in mathematics education. The positive outcomes reported by the respondents corresponded with themes such as fostering positive mathematical identities and the role of informal learning environments in supporting STEM education.

Furthermore, the responses were consistent with theoretical frameworks such as Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and Communities of Practice (CoP), which emphasize autonomy, competence, and collaborative learning environments in driving intrinsic motivation and skill development.

Impact of Teacher Facilitator

The impact of teacher facilitators during the Math Learning Camp (NLC) played a crucial role in shaping students' experiences and outcomes in mathematical learning. In this section, we delve into the results and discussions regarding the influence of teacher facilitators on students' engagement, learning strategies, and overall mathematical identity formation within the NLC context.

"The teacher facilitator let us discover our capabilities and potential on acing the different math problems I like the teacher facilitator because he let us discover our capabilities." -G7S1

"I really enjoyed lectures because that's the time that you can ask questions to the teacher and our teacher is really good at explaining the concept that's why we really understood the lesson very well. The teacher facilitator repeating discussions was immensely helpful in enhancing my understanding of mathematical concepts. When my classmates couldn't provide assistance, I didn't hesitate to approach the math teacher for help."-G8S3.

"I asked the teacher facilitator if it's okay to repeat the discussion for our own sake, and he granted it. He rediscussed it and afterwards, the majority of us knew already." -G8S4

"The personalized attention and guidance from teachers during NLC make it feel like I'm receiving private tutoring, which greatly enhances my understanding of challenging math concepts." -G8S5

The statements from G7S1 highlighted the significant role of teacher facilitators in fostering a supportive learning environment, aligning with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which emphasized autonomy in fostering intrinsic motivation. By allowing students to discover their capabilities, teacher facilitators enhanced their confidence and ownership over their learning journey, positively impacting their academic performance.

G7S3 emphasized the importance of effective teaching methods, resonating with research findings on the significance of clear explanations and interactive strategies in promoting deep learning. The supportive environment facilitated by teacher facilitators encouraged students to seek clarification, contributing to their comprehension of mathematical concepts.

G8S3 and G8S4 highlighted the effectiveness of repetition and reinforcement in learning, consistent with Social Identity Theory (SIT) principles of repeated exposure strengthening individuals' identification with the subject matter. Teacher facilitators' willingness to repeat discussions reinforced understanding and fostered a sense of belonging within the learning community.

G8S5's statement underscored the personalized attention provided by teacher facilitators, aligning with Communities of Practice (CoP) principles where collaborative environments support knowledge sharing. Personalized guidance improves learning outcomes and student engagement.

The emphasis on autonomy and discovery aligns with Self-Determination Theory (SDT), supporting intrinsic motivation and autonomy in learning. Effective explanation and understanding were supported by research indicating that clear explanations and interactive teaching methods enhance learning outcomes. The practice of repetition and reinforcement is consistent with Social Identity Theory (SIT), emphasizing repeated exposure in shaping identities and group affiliations. Personalized attention and guidance are supported by studies highlighting the benefits of individualized support in improving learning outcomes.

Challenges in Group Cooperation and Leadership

In the National Learning Camp (NLC), where students gathered to enhance their mathematical skills and understanding, challenges in group cooperation and leadership often emerged. This section delved into the experiences and observations of subjects regarding these challenges, as shared through their feedback.

"In fun-filled activities, I encountered misunderstanding with my groupmates due to different ideas and not listening to suggestions of the leaders. And also, some of my groupmates don't know how to process the lesson and can't do the task given by the leader. So, as I leader I instructed some of my groupmates who already knew the process that they will be taking charge with our classmates who still find the process a lot difficult." – G7S4

"As a leader, I need to lower down my temper so that the members will follow you. But sometimes, when my temper burst, some words uttered negatively. And also, I need to do my task to tutor them to the best of my ability so that they will be able to know the concept whenever the teacher asks them how to do so." -G8S1

"I encountered difficulties as a leader because most of my members are girls, and they don't really like math and they don't know how to solve mathematical problems. But I taught them the best that I could. I really want to win the game, but I can't carry my members because they're not interested in the activity. I don't have any choice because they have lacked interest in the game." -G8S2

The responses outlined various challenges learners faced in group cooperation and leadership at the National Learning Camp (NLC), including misunderstandings, difficulty processing lessons, and varying levels of interest. Effective communication and active listening were crucial to mitigate misunderstandings and foster collaboration, aligning with findings from Graven & Heyd-Metzuyanin (2019). Encouraging open dialogue and respecting diverse perspectives promoted a positive learning environment.

Leadership strategies discussed in the literature (NCTM, 2018a; Midgley et al., 2018) emphasized the importance of patient guidance and instructional support. Learners could apply these principles to guide their group members effectively through mathematical tasks. Additionally, leveraging research on motivation (After-School Alliance, 2021) can help educators design activities that enhance learners' interest and engagement in mathematics-related tasks. Applying these insights could improve overall participation and learning outcomes within the NLC environment.

Use of Online Resources for Advanced Study

In this section, it delved into the utilization of online resources for advanced study among learners. The responses of the subjects were utilized to gain insights into their experiences and perceptions regarding the use of online resources for advanced study.

“At home, whenever I didn’t understand the lesson in school, I keep on practicing it and solve it again and again to get the correct answers. I searched it on Brainly and Google (online learning resources).” – G7S3 “Sometimes, I would study and search on YouTube on how to solve a specific problem. Because in YouTube there are many tutorials.” -G7S4

Subjects emphasized the crucial role of online resources, such as Brainly, Google, and YouTube, in supporting their mathematics learning. These platforms offered tutorials and explanations catering to various learning preferences, allowing students to revisit challenging topics at their own pace. Their reliance on online resources showcased their initiative and motivation for self-directed learning, supplementing classroom instruction conveniently. The flexibility of accessing materials anytime and anywhere accommodated diverse learning schedules and preferences. Access to a wide range of online tutorials enriched students' understanding of mathematical concepts beyond traditional classroom settings. These findings align with literature emphasizing the benefits of leveraging online resources for personalized learning experiences in STEM subjects like mathematics according to After-School Alliance (2021).

Impact of NLC on Addressing Gender Stereotypes

The statements provided by the students reflect common gender stereotypes related to math performance and interest. The belief that boys were inherently better at math than girls is a pervasive stereotype that has been debunked by research. However, these stereotypes can still influence students' attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors towards math.

“Boys in the class can do better in Math than girls.” -G7S1

“I encountered difficulties as a leader because most of my members are girls, and they don’t really like math and they don’t know how to solve mathematical problems. But I taught them the best that I could. I really want to win the game, but I can’t carry my members because they’re not interested in the activity. I don’t have any choice because they have lacked interest in the game.” – G8S2

The first statement from G7P1 reinforced the stereotype that boys were naturally more adept at math than girls. This belief could lead to biased expectations and treatment of students based on their gender, potentially affecting girls' confidence and performance in math.

The second statement from G8S2 illustrated the impact of gender stereotypes on students' attitudes towards math. The student struggled as a leader because their group members, who are mostly girls, lack interest and confidence in math. This reflected how gender stereotypes could contribute to a self-fulfilling prophecy, where girls may internalize beliefs about their supposed inferiority in math, leading to disengagement and avoidance of mathematical activities.

Gender stereotypes could negatively impact girls' self-perception and confidence in their math abilities, leading to reduced participation and achievement in math-related activities.

Students like G8S2 may experience challenges in leadership roles if they perceive their team members as less capable based on gender stereotypes. This could hinder collaborative learning and teamwork. Addressing and challenging gender stereotypes was essential for promoting equity in education. All students should have equal opportunities to engage with and excel in math, regardless of their gender.

According to Spelke (2018) there was no inherent gender difference in math ability. Beliefs about gender differences in math performance were socially constructed and perpetuated through stereotypes. (Eccles, 2019) said that gender stereotypes could influence students' academic performance and career aspirations, particularly in STEM fields Eccles (2019). Stoet and Geary (2018) mentioned that interventions aimed at challenging gender stereotypes and promoting positive attitudes towards math have been shown to improve girls' performance and interest in the subject.

Problem 2: What action plan can be designed based on the result of the study?

Rationale

This action plan, stretching from July 2024 to May 2025, was designed to address multiple facets of learning and instruction that contribute to a student’s mathematical development. It acknowledged that students’ performance, engagement, and motivation in mathematics were influenced not just by how they were taught but also by how they perceive themselves in relation to the subject.

Implementing differentiated instruction, developing contextualized learning resources, and integrating peer mentoring, gender sensitivity, and multilingual support into the curriculum, the action plan aimed to create an educational environment where all students feel valued, understood, and supported in their learning journeys. These strategies were chosen to meet students at their level of understanding, adapt to their cultural contexts, encourage their social skills, and address any barriers to learning, such as language proficiency and gender biases.

The overarching goal was to enhance each student's mathematical identity in a holistic way—boosting their confidence, nurturing their curiosity, and increasing their capacity to engage with mathematical concepts deeply and critically. This comprehensive approach

ensures that improvements in math performance go hand-in-hand with positive changes in students' attitudes and perceptions towards the subject, laying a solid foundation for lifelong mathematical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Conclusions

The research conducted on the National Learning Camp (NLC) has provided valuable insights into its positive aspects, challenges, and impact on students' learning experiences. Through the exploration of student perspectives, related literature, and theoretical frameworks, this study has contributed to a deeper understanding of the NLC's role in fostering students' mathematical identity formation and promoting STEM education.

The findings of this research highlighted the progress made in recognizing the importance of innovative educational initiatives like the NLC in enhancing students' mathematical abilities and engagement. By identifying positive aspects such as the camp's impact on critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and collaboration, as well as addressing challenges like gender stereotypes and group cooperation issues, this research has paved the way for informed interventions and improvements in STEM education programs.

Furthermore, this research served as a useful tool for educators, policymakers, and program organizers seeking to enhance students' learning experiences and promote equitable access to STEM education. By understanding the factors influencing students' engagement and learning outcomes within initiatives like the NLC, stakeholders could implement targeted interventions and strategies to address challenges effectively and maximize the benefits of such programs.

The research conducted on the National Learning Camp (NLC) represented a significant contribution to the field of STEM education and educational psychology. By shedding light on the dynamics of informal learning environments, the role of teacher facilitators, and the impact of collaborative learning experiences, this research informed evidence-based practices aimed at fostering students' academic growth and holistic development in mathematics and beyond.

Based on the results and conclusion, the following recommendations are presented to:

DepEd officials may conduct vertically aligned training and workshops addressing teachers' needs in improving students' engagement, performance, and motivation in mathematics. Additionally, they should provide extended professional development opportunities for teachers and ensure the provision of contextualized learning resources to cater to diverse learners.

School principals may support teachers by effectively communicating policy guidelines, addressing resource gaps, and prioritizing teacher coaching and mentoring for improved program implementation.

Teachers may utilize diverse learning materials, incorporate interactive games, provide professional training on activity tools and methods, conduct intensive training for 21st-century classroom practices, facilitate diverse learner engagement and assessment, and collaborate for improved professional development.

Reading coordinators may support teachers develop contextualized learning resources and collaborate with them to ensure that materials align with K- 12 competencies.

Learners may actively participate in diverse learning activities and engage with interactive games to enhance their understanding and enjoyment of mathematics.

Future researchers may conduct further sampling that includes different types and locations of schools, as well as learners' perceptions of National Learning Camp practices, to enhance understanding of mathematics education practices and outcomes.

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